

**FORMATION OF GENERAL COMPETENCES AND COMPETENCIES OF
DEVELOPMENTAL AREAS IN CHILDREN DURING THE EDUCATIONAL
PROCESS IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS**

Abdullaeva Nigora Akromjonovna

*Andijan region, Khojaabad district, head of the branch
of Preschool education department DNMTMFUMShTE*

Annotation: *The main goal of the reforms implemented in our country is different is to bring up a mature and perfect generation. Perfect generation spiritual and moral education is of special importance in education, before school The educational stage is the most important period of personality formation and development is considered In the article, the implementation of spiritual and moral education in preschool education the main directions, relevance and social, pedagogical foundations of improvement scientifically analyzed. Necessary suggestions and recommendations are given.*

Key words: *spirituality, enlightenment, education, interdisciplinary integration, didactics, concept, moral culture, creative skills, social competence, "mass culture", universal values.*

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It is known that today's globalization, the world-wide ideological ideological struggles, to destroy the national values of nations focused "mass culture" and the influence of foreign ideas from any country requires paying special attention to the issue of spirituality. In turn Only persons with high moral education can serve for the development of the country active, concerned with the country's problems and achievements can be citizens with civil status. Such is the citizenship implementation of education from the pre-school stage of education is appropriate. In recent years, the field of preschool education in our country development, radical renewal of its activities, advanced foreign in the field introduction of experiences and innovations, training of highly qualified personnel great work is being done in the field. Republic of Uzbekistan President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 8, 2019 approval of the concept of development of the educational system until 2030 on" Resolution No. PQ-4312 of the Cabinet of Ministers, 13 of 2019 In May — Pre-school educational institutions continued their activities Resolution No. 391 on improvement measures serving as an important legal basis for reforms.

The main goal of these reforms is an all-round mature and well-rounded society from the effective implementation of education from the stage of preschool education consists of As President Sh.Mirziyoev noted, "from the birth of a child starting, in which intellectual activity increases precisely at preschool age, moral- aesthetic and physical characteristics are formed". Today's most relevant

One of the tasks is a new, systematic approach to education, support in the child family,

preschool education, general in the guaranteed formation of qualities education, secondary vocational and higher educational institutions, neighborhoods and between them to fully reveal their socio-pedagogical potential requires raising the scientific-methodical integrity to a new level. Resolution No. 1059 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 31, 2019 3 - 6 (7) in the "Concept of Continuous Spiritual Education" approved by spiritual upbringing of young children, personal qualities in them, including their own managing emotions, awakening social motives, to national traditions needs such as developing interest, caring for loved ones formation as the priorities of spiritual and moral education is set.

The pedagogy of the preschool educational institution is spiritual and moral in children when starting to compose adjectives, first of all, its content and deep understanding of the essence and educational and educational activities conducted with children should follow it in educational work. First of all, it should be noted that Spirituality is one of the integrative fields in its content and essence enters. After all, as its structural components;

- firstly, moral standards are recognized.
- secondly, "philosophical, legal, scientific, artistic, religious and

It is also wide because it has such a set of ideas and concepts is a networked, comprehensive, in a word, integrated field. Also, spirituality is "the mutual relations of people, their value system formed and developed during life experiences" If we understand that, since it (i.e., spirituality) is a system, in turn, as we mentioned, it is multifaceted, moreover, throughout the life of mankind forms and enriches. The next generation is an integrative field in this way as it will be absorbed and enriched. Preschool education is a process is important as an initial syllable.

Preschool education with modern trends in the education of children an integrative approach to their spiritual and moral education based on historical educational experiences and values of our people Today's important issue is, so to speak, a social demand is considered Because today's preschool age child the extent of the directly presented information, their integrative content and is causing teaching needs based on the methodology. of integration The main categories are general communication, interaction, integrity, and systematicity organized and essentially consistent with philosophical categories and acquires important methodological and didactic value in education. Integrated education makes the individual intellectual and cultural as the main factor of development, first of all, the conditions of existence, change processes and cases of connection with other events as a whole is to convey to the minds of children [6]. As noted by academician I.P. Pavlov, education and upbringing process, various communication related to human activity, consists of thought, thinking and knowledge. In his opinion, interaction between disciplines Coherence is the lens of existing coherence between the events of nature and society is a reflection. In the spiritual and moral upbringing of children of preschool age some pedagogical conditions of using integrated education the following should be taken into account as conditions:

1. Educator's readiness for innovative activities.
 - a) educators' knowledge, skills and the acquisition of qualifications.
 - b) the ability to put integrated education into practice existence.
2. Didactic, methodical and availability of technical support.

3. Motivational preparation of children for integrated education provide.

4. Foreign countries in the organization of integrated education using their experiences. L. G. Savenkova conducts education and upbringing work with children that it is necessary to develop a single program for pedagogues and educators will fly. A number of developmental activities in the development of such a program shows the types separately. Also, scholars for different age groups emphasizes that they differ in importance. To this methodology as the integrative foundations of spiritual and moral education the following can be mentioned separately, namely:

- in the content of events observed by children in the environment to understand the spiritual and moral content and about them in an elementary way to create the necessary conditions for them to have personal imagination;

- the social environment in which the child receives education and upbringing (kindergarten, family and b.) the world of objects, events and processes to the child's age, ensuring compatibility with the level of intellectual formation;

- in children educational and aimed at the formation of spiritual and moral qualities content and methods, forms and means of educational work of children pay attention to color depending on age;

- the priority direction of spiritual and moral education, a special "bullet hole" and the topics that are its structural components, ensure that training is organically and logically related to each other;

- the process of forming spiritual and moral ideas in children activator, the process of assimilation of the presented materials conducting complex activities that increase the level of consciousness;

- the content of the process of moral and moral upbringing of children, methodology, forms and tools based on the principles of regularity pay special attention to the construction, etc. Spiritual and moral upbringing of children of preschool age as the main pedagogical features of an integrative approach to the issue of the following can be specified separately.

Education in preschool educational institutions to carry out work at the level of the requirements of the time, developing it. Going trends are complex to the process of formation of children as individuals requires an approach. In this regard, they interacted with the training organization based on educational principles is an important didactic requirement.

In short, an educator in preschool educational institutions to set up activities correctly, to organize integrated training conditions for the holistic formation of spiritual and moral qualities in children creates. Spiritual and moral education of children of preschool age regularity of the process and among the pedagogical features of education. Following the principle of logical development is ultimately his guarantees a positive outcome.

References:

1. <https://president.uz/uz/lists/view/4057>

2. <https://lex.uz/docs/4676839>.

3. Decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 31.12.2019 No. 1059

of

4. An explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language. J. II. - T.: "Uzbek National Encyclopedia" State scientific publishing house, 2006. - 672 p.
5. Philosophy: an encyclopedic dictionary. - T.: "Sharq" NMAK, 2004. -496 p.
6. Zunnunov A., Sulaymanov A. Educational subjects in the educational process integration factors. - T.: 2004.– 29 p.
7. Savenkova L.G. – Pedagogical conditions of integrated learning visual arts in public school. - M.: 2001., 101 p.

